

An Extremely Nearby, Extremely Low-Mass, Extremely Isolated Dwarf Galaxy

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My collaborators and I recently discovered the Pavo dwarf galaxy, one of the lowest mass star-forming galaxies known. It was identified via a novel search technique that relied on machine learning classification of galaxy candidates identified in the [DESI Legacy Imaging Surveys](#) (using data collected at Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory and Kitt Peak National Observatory, both Programs of NSF’s NOIRLab, and at the University of Arizona’s Steward Observatory). Despite only being 2 Mpc away, Pavo is also remarkably isolated, with no other known galaxy within 600 kpc. Its minute stellar mass, estimated to be just $4 \times 10^5 M_{\odot}$, combined with its isolation make Pavo an ideal target for understanding how star formation proceeds in some of the lowest mass galaxies in the universe. Full details of the discovery are published in Jones et al. (2023).

Figure 1: IMACS g+r color image of Pavo. The central regions of Pavo are dominated by the blue light of young stars, but its stellar body can be traced out to the white dotted ellipse. The orange dashed ellipse shows a region that mostly contains old red giant branch stars that were used to determine the distance to Pavo. There is a particularly bright star near the center of Pavo; however, this star has measurable proper motion and is therefore a foreground object. It is crossed out with a red x in the figure.

The gravitational potential wells of the lowest mass galaxies are so shallow that the gas they contained in the early Universe was not dense enough to self-shield from any external UV radiation. During cosmic reionization, when the Universe first began forming stars en masse, these galaxies lost all of their cold gas, never to regain it again. Thus, reionization is thought to have

permanently quenched their star formation. At marginally higher dark matter halo masses, the potential wells of galaxies were just deep enough to retain (or re-accrete) some cold gas and thus continue forming stars to the present day. These are therefore the lowest mass star-forming galaxies in today’s Universe, and Pavo is one of just a few such galaxies that are currently known.

Pavo was discovered with a modified version of the SMUDGes (Zaritsky et al. 2019) pipeline, which was originally intended to identify much more distant low surface brightness galaxies. The initial search catalog contained hundreds of thousands of candidates across the full Legacy Surveys footprint, far too many to inspect manually. These were passed to a convolutional neural network (CNN) classifier that had been trained on known nearby objects including low-mass star-forming galaxies, ultra-faint dwarfs, and Milky Way globular clusters. This CNN filtered out the enormous number of spurious and uninteresting objects picked up in the initial search, selecting just those most likely to be extremely low-mass, nearby galaxies, one of which was Pavo. Rapid follow-up imaging with the Inamori-Magellan Areal Camera and Spectrograph on the Magellan Baade Telescope resolved the brightest stars in Pavo, revealing the existence of both an ancient and a young stellar population. The tip of the red giant branch in the color-magnitude diagram was used as a standard candle to estimate the distance to Pavo as 2 Mpc.

Given this distance and its location in the sky, Pavo is extraordinarily isolated, with no known neighboring galaxy within over 600 kpc. This isolation is key and makes Pavo an ideal laboratory to study how star formation proceeds in such exceptionally low-mass galaxies. Although cosmic reionization is expected to have a strong influence on the gas and early star formation in these

Figure 2: Supergalactic XY projection showing all nearby galaxies with known distances. The Local Group is in the center. Pavo and several other notable nearby, extremely low mass dwarfs are highlighted. Both Leo P and Tucana B are considered isolated, but Pavo's isolation is even more extreme. It is in a direction away from any known nearby structure. Its apparent nearest neighbors are only nearby in projection. In three dimensions Pavo has no known neighbor within over 600 kpc.

galaxies, there is very little direct observational evidence for what those effects are. The evidence that does exist comes almost exclusively from low-mass galaxies within the Local Group. However, given their low masses, these galaxies are also highly susceptible to environmental effects, such as ram pressure and tidal stripping. As there is no way to know definitively how long satellites galaxies within the Local Group have been group members, it is impossible to conclusively separate the imprint of reionization on their star formation histories from those that resulted from environmental effects.

Thus, extremely low-mass galaxies such as Pavo, that are close enough to study in detail with space telescopes yet still far enough away to be isolated, are a scarce but vital resource for understanding the evolution of the lowest mass galaxies.

References

- Jones, M. G., et al. 2023, *ApJL*, 957, 5
- Zaritsky, D. 2019, *ApJS*, 240, 1